

Participants:

1. Principal
2. Vice Principal
3. Teacher

Interviewer:

Vinsensius Bawa Toron

Time:

March 26, 2025 at 08.00 -10.00 Indonesia WITA

Venue:

1. SMP Negeri 1 Larantuka
2. SMP Negeri 2 Larantuka
3. Batu Payung State Junior High School
4. SMP Mater Inviolata

A. The Dimension of Faith and Noble Character

(Aligned with Tonga Danga Values)

1. "Spiritual activities are going well, but not all students are showing behavioral changes." (Teacher)
2. "There are still students who are diligent in worship but their attitude does not reflect moral values." (WKS)
3. "Not all students make the value of faith a personal awareness." (KS)

B. Dimensions of Mutual Cooperation

(In line with the Values of Pohen Haben & Tedun Toda)

1. "Students are willing to cooperate if directed." (Teacher)
2. "Student participation usually arises when there is a school program." (WKS)
3. "It hasn't become a spontaneous habit yet." (KS)

C. Independent Dimension

(Aligned with Tonga Danga Values)

1. "Some students are still waiting for the teacher's direction." (Teacher)
2. "Independent learning initiatives are not evenly distributed." (Deputy Principal)
3. "Awareness of personal responsibility is still low." (Principal)

D. Critical Reasoning Dimension

(In line with the value of Gasik Arik)

1. "Students dare to express their opinions, but sometimes they are not polite."
(Teacher)
2. "Classroom discussions are active, but the ethics of dialogue need to be built."
(Deputy Principal)
3. "Critical skills are not always accompanied by an attitude of appreciation."
(Principal)

E. Global Diversity Dimension

(Integration of Local Cultural Values)

1. "Students are quite tolerant of differences." (Teacher)
2. "But local culture hasn't been referenced much in interactions." (Deputy Principal)
3. "Local cultural identity needs to be strengthened." (Principal)